

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS OF RESORCIN-FORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMER IN THE PRESENCE OF A NANOPARTICLE AND OBTAINING SULFOCATIONITE ON ITS BASIS

Naibova T.M.,

*Honored professor of the Department of
"Technology of organic substances and high-molecular compounds"
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Azadliq 20, Baku, Azerbaijan
ORCID: 0000-0001-5543-1033*

Mammadova A.A.,

*Assistant of the Department of
"Technology of organic substances and high-molecular compounds"
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Azadliq 20, Baku, Azerbaijan
ORCID: 0000-0002-6828-2628*

Abbasova K.Q.,

*Assistant of the Department of
"Technology of organic substances and high-molecular compounds"
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Azadliq 20, Baku, Azerbaijan
ORCID: 0000-0001-8327-0791*

Memmedzade N.R.

*Magistr of the Department of
"Technology of organic substances and high-molecular compounds"
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Azadliq 20, Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

Thermosetting oligomer-based materials represent one of the important directions in the modern chemical industry. The main advantage of these materials is that during the oligomerization process they undergo irreversible chemical transformations, resulting in materials characterized by high mechanical strength, heat resistance, and chemical stability.

Sulfocationites based on thermosetting oligomers exhibit high thermal and chemical stability, which makes them suitable for use in environments of various chemical nature. In addition, their high ion-exchange capacity plays an important role in applications such as water purification and processes in the oil and gas industry. At the same time, the use of cation-exchange materials in wastewater treatment is of particular importance from the perspective of environmental protection.

The principal function of sulfocationites is the adsorption of cations from different solutions through the ion-exchange mechanism. Owing to this property, sulfonated oligomers are indispensable in processes such as water softening and desalination, gas purification, and the separation of non-ferrous metals from ores in the metallurgical industry.

Thermosetting oligomer-based sulfocationites possess a cross-linked structure, which provides high resistance both to elevated temperatures and to aggressive chemical environments.

The synthesis of sulfocationites generally involves two main stages. First, oligomerization of functional monomers is carried out (typically by the polycondensation method). Subsequently, ionogenic groups are introduced into the structure of the obtained oligomer through an appropriate chemical transformation reaction.

The production of sulfocationites is performed not only on an industrial scale but also in scientific research laboratories. The main goal in synthesizing these materials is to increase their ion-exchange capacity, improve their mechanical and thermal stability, and enhance their selectivity. In recent years, significant progress has been achieved in the development of a new generation of cation-exchange materials based on nanomaterials and hybrid compositions.

In the present study, the main properties of resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer synthesized in the presence of nanoparticles and the sulfocationite obtained on its basis were investigated.

Keywords: thermosetting, polycondensation, resorcinol-formaldehyde oligomer, silicon dioxide, nanoparticles, sulfonation, sulfocationite

Introduction

In modern materials science, research aimed at obtaining new hybrid systems through the synthesis of

functional-group-containing organic and inorganic compounds with nanoparticles is considered an important and relevant scientific direction. Such

systems combine the flexibility, processability, and chemical reactivity of organic compounds with the high mechanical strength, thermal resistance, and chemical stability of inorganic reagents. As a result, materials with distinctive structural and functional properties are obtained [1].

Macromolecular systems based on resorcinol–formaldehyde (RF) are of particular importance. Oligomers formed through the polycondensation reaction of resorcinol and formaldehyde exhibit high chemical and thermal stability and possess the ability to form porous structures. These characteristics make RF-based systems promising for the preparation of sulfocationites, catalyst supports, aerogel structures, and porous carbon materials [2–4].

Among inorganic components, silicon dioxide (SiO_2) nanoparticles play a significant role in the preparation of nanostructured materials due to their high specific surface area, chemical stability, and surface functionalization capability. Their functional groups can effectively interact with oligomer chains, promoting the formation of nanostructured systems. This approach is advantageous for achieving both homogeneous dispersion and structural stability of the resulting materials [5–7].

The functionalization of nanoparticle-containing resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomers through the sulfonation process is of particular importance. The RF oligomer reacts with concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), resulting in enrichment with sulfonic groups ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$). During this process, sulfocationites are formed and adsorbed on the material surface. The presence of sulfocationites increases the ion-exchange capacity of the material, helps preserve the porous structure, and enhances its ability to adsorb heavy metal ions [8].

The formation of sulfocationites is not limited only to the introduction of functional groups. At the same time, stable electrostatic interactions are formed between the oligomer network and the particle surface, resulting in homogeneous, porous, and chemically active hybrid materials [9].

Thus, the synthesis of RF oligomers in the presence of SiO_2 nanoparticles followed by sulfonation leading to the formation of sulfocationites has both scientific and practical significance. Studies in this direction enable a deeper understanding of the synthesis mechanism, structural characteristics, and functional properties of such materials. Cation-exchange materials of different grades differ in their main parameters and in the degree of polycondensation. As the degree of polycondensation increases, samples with lower specific volume are obtained, which significantly affects the static and dynamic ion-exchange capacities of the resulting cationites. Therefore, the synthesis of sulfocationites with new compositions and the investigation of their properties, including ion-exchange capacity and chemical stability within different pH ranges, are essential. The preparation of thermosetting oligomer-based sulfocationites and the investigation of their properties are therefore of considerable theoretical and practical relevance. Ion-exchange materials are not simple

chemical substances but rather multicomponent systems formed on the basis of high-molecular-weight compounds with different molecular weights. For this reason, it is difficult to determine their exact chemical structure, molecular weight, and some physicochemical parameters. The main characteristics of ion-exchange materials—such as sorption capacity, degree of cross-linking, conductivity, ion-exchange capacity, and swelling degree—are largely determined by the chemical nature of their macromolecular structure. One of the important factors affecting these properties is the pore size of the oligomer framework. Larger pore cells facilitate the penetration of larger ions into the oligomer matrix; however, this may simultaneously reduce the mechanical strength of the material [12–14].

Sulfonation of functionalized oligomers through analogous transformation reactions can also occur in the presence of various functional groups.

Experimental section

In this study, the following chemicals were used: resorcinol ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})_2$), an aqueous 37% solution of formaldehyde, silicon dioxide (SiO_2) nanoparticles, and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 98%). Resorcinol and formaldehyde were employed as the initial reagents for the synthesis of resorcinol–formaldehyde (RF) oligomer. Silicon dioxide nanoparticles were introduced into the system in order to promote the formation of the oligomer structure and to improve its main properties. Sulfuric acid was used for the sulfonation of the material and for the introduction of sulfonic groups into the system. All chemicals were of analytical grade and were used without additional purification. Distilled water was used during the preparation of solutions and throughout the experimental procedures. The resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer was synthesized by the well-known method based on the non-equilibrium polycondensation reaction of resorcinol and formaldehyde [10–11].

The synthesized nanoparticle-containing resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer was homogenized, and the resulting mixture was kept in a water bath at a temperature of 50 °C until gel formation occurred. The oligomer obtained by the sol–gel method was subsequently dried. Drying was carried out in a vacuum-type laboratory oven at 105 °C until a constant weight was achieved (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer synthesized in the presence of nanoparticles

To impart ion-exchange properties to the resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer synthesized in the presence of nanoparticles, the material was subjected to sulfonation with sulfuric acid. For this purpose, a

predetermined amount of the nanoparticle-containing oligomer was placed into a laboratory reactor with a volume of 250 mL equipped with a reflux condenser and a thermometer. Concentrated sulfuric acid (98%) was then added to the reactor, and the mixture was stirred at a temperature of 140 °C while the analogous transformation process was carried out (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Synthesis of nanoparticle-containing RF oligomer-based sulfocationite

After the system became homogeneous, the reaction mass was cooled to room temperature. Subsequently, a 37% aqueous solution of formaldehyde was added to the mixture. The reaction mixture was then placed in an oil bath maintained at a temperature of 110 °C, and the curing process was carried out for 2 hours (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Nanoparticle-containing RF oligomer-based sulfocationite

After completion of the reaction, the obtained material was washed with distilled water until the washing water became clear.

The resulting ion-exchange material is a black solid substance, insoluble in water and hydrocarbons, and exhibits sulfocationite properties (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Prepared sulfocationite

Subsequently, the product was dried and fractionated into particles with a size range of 1–3 mm. The structure of the sulfocationite was investigated using infrared (IR) spectroscopy [15]. The results of the spectral analysis confirmed the expected structure of the sulfocationite and verified the occurrence of the sulfonation process.

Specifically, the absorption band observed at 3347 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching vibrations of $-\text{OH}$ groups. The peaks detected in the region of 811 cm^{-1} and 759 cm^{-1} are attributed to deformation vibrations of $-\text{CH}$ groups in the aromatic ring, while the bands in the 1500–1450 cm^{-1} region are associated with vibrations of the aromatic benzene ring. Characteristic functional groups of sulfocationites, namely $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups, were confirmed by absorption bands in the 1450–1350 cm^{-1} region corresponding to stretching vibrations, as well as bands in the 1100–1070 cm^{-1} region, which are associated with vibrations attributed to nanoparticles (Figure 5).

Figure 5. IR spectrum of the sulfocationite

The main characteristics of the nanoparticle-containing resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer-based sulfocationite, as well as a reference resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer-based sulfocationite prepared for comparative purposes, were investigated.

Main parameters of resorcinol–formaldehyde and nanoparticle-containing resorcinol–formaldehyde oligomer-based sulfocationites

№	Parameters	Sulfocationites	
		RFO-based sulfocationite	Nanoparticle-containing RFO-based sulfocationite
1	Appearance	Dark brown	Black
2	Swelling degree, %	0.22	0.18
3	Specific volume, mL/g	2.84	3.05
4	True density, kg/m ³	1081	1120
5	Static ion-exchange capacity, mg eq/g	1.88	2.05
6	Dynamic exchange capacity, mgeq/g	0.74	0.82
7	Particle size	0.7-1.5	0.5-1.2
8	Bulk density, g/mL	0.63	0.58

Conclusion

Both RFO-based and nanoparticle-containing RFO-based sulfocationites are insoluble in any solvents. As a result of the sulfonation of RFO with sulfuric acid, homogeneous, porous, and ion-exchange sulfocationites were obtained. IR spectral analysis confirmed the presence of –OH groups, benzene ring structures, and –SO₃H functional groups. Based on the IR spectra, the existence of these functional groups was verified. The introduction of sulfonic groups enhanced the ion-exchange capacity of the sulfocationites, ensured the preservation of the porous structure, and facilitated stable interactions between the oligomer matrix and the SiO₂ surface. Thus, the prepared sulfocationites are structurally and functionally stable and demonstrate strong potential for metal ion adsorption, catalytic processes, and other environmental applications.

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